

Title: Giving 'Big Data' a Conscience: How to Create Ethical Big Data Research

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Introduction: More and more frequently researchers who have the intention to conduct ethical research have inadvertently collected 'big data' that can create significant moral harm to others. Despite being aware of this possibility and being motivated to address both known and unknown problems of big data collection and use, it has been unclear how best to resolve this moral problem for individual researchers.

Aim: The data itself does not have a moral compass or conscience but involves information about human individuals and this fact alone has moral implications for how we treat the information collected. The aim for researchers is to still be enabled to conduct their valuable research and to do so ethically despite the unique challenges big data presents.

Conclusions: The solution in part is to realize that we need to rethink how we think about data and treat the data more like people, like 'subjects', and not as 'objects'. By reframing how we consider the data collected we, through our own moral sense, can give big data a conscience, our own.

Keywords: big data, ethics, decision making, data collection

Biography: Sandra Dreisbach has a Phd in Philosophy is currently a lecturer at University of California, Santa Cruz in both the Philosophy and Bimolecular Engineering Departments. As an ethicist her research focuses on ethical decision making and moral psychology. Sandra has also worked for several years in the tech industry in both hardware and software engineering departments working for large companies like Apple as well as small start-up

companies. Sandra is also an affiliate of the UCSC Center for Public Philosophy and is one of the founders of Ethical Resolve, an ethics consulting company and is an affiliate consultant for them.